

Response to DESNZ consultation on: The Home Energy Model – Energy Performance Certificates

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Section 1: How the introduction of HEM could change how existing buildings are assessed

Question 1: Do you agree with the introduction of a modular approach to data input for existing builds, where assessors can enter complete data where available and rely on defaults for other elements?

Response options: strongly agree, agree, neither agree nor disagree, disagree or strongly disagree. Please provide any comments or evidence to support your answer.

Agree – The modular approach is consistent with the proposed Tiered data input for the Demand Flexibility Certification (DFC) framework¹, which was meant to address data availability issues, maximising the utility of existing data.

Caveats: see views in Q2

Question 2: Please share your views on the following potential impacts of a modular approach.

a. Quality of assessments and EPCs:

- *assessment accuracy*
- *trust, usability, or consistency in EPCs*
- *how inputs are communicated to consumers/householders*

b. Impact on assessors' workloads, costs, training, and skills?

c. Implementation risks, for example: QA/audit and fraud risk, supply-chain readiness and training needs

d. Anything else you feel is relevant.

a. Every effort should be made to ensure that the new modular approach is at least as accurate as the current EPC approach – however inaccurate this existing approach may be. Moreover, it should be ensured that the use of the new, property-specific data is in fact delivering accuracy increases, and not just “not interfering” with additional calculations. This means that the modular approach must not be limited to data input; it should encompass a set of corresponding modular methodologies to make the most of available data.

¹ www.edrc.ac.uk/publications/demand-flexibility-certificates

b. Any potential impact on assessors' workloads is presumably offset by the benefits of more accurate assessment. As regards to cost-benefit analyses, this is certainly something that would need to be closely monitored, perhaps as part of a pilot study.

Question 4:

If a modular approach is adopted, the term "Reduced data HEM" (RdHEM) may not accurately reflect the model's structure or purpose. We want to ensure the terminology clearly conveys this flexibility and avoids confusion with previous approaches. A clear, intuitive name will help stakeholders understand the purpose of the methodology and distinguish it from both full HEM and legacy RdSAP. Potential options for the new name are:

- *HEM for Existing Dwellings (HEMEX)*
- *HEM Input Expansion (HEMIE)*
- *Mixed Data for HEM (MdHEM), or*
- *Reduced data HEM (RdHEM).*

Do you have any views on the proposed alternative name(s) that would better capture the intent and flexibility of a modular version of HEM? Do you have any other suggested options that are not listed above?

Alternative: Modular Augmented Input for HEM (MAIHEM)

Section 2: Fabric performance metric

Question 5: Do you agree with the proposal to evaluate fabric performance using FEE?

Response options: strongly agree, agree, neither agree nor disagree, disagree or strongly disagree. Please provide any additional comments or evidence to support your answer.

Agree – A specific metric to assess fabric performance is definitely necessary. This is also consistent with the EFC approach which considers Basal flexibility metrics that explicitly assess the thermal performance of buildings. The Fabric Energy Efficiency (FEE) methodology appears to be reasonably sound. However, care should be taken not to rely too heavily on "standardisation" of heating/cooling demands as this runs the risk of compromising the accuracy of the assessments.

Question 6: Do you agree with the approach to maintain broad equivalence between the C/D boundary in the current EER rating and the C/D boundary in the Fabric Performance Metric?

Response options: strongly agree, agree, neither agree nor disagree, disagree or strongly disagree. Please provide any additional comments or evidence to support your answer, including evidence on the sorts of measures that should be prioritised under this metric.

Disagree – Scoring/banding “equivalence” concerns should not be a determining factor on decisions around whether to implement a more accurate methodology / more suitable set of metrics. Any sensible methodology should be able to continue to reflect the benefits of any building energy efficiency improvements as a matter of course. Differences between scores produced by the old and the new methodologies are inconsequential, as the banding is (or should be) done relative to scores produced by the same methodology.

Question 7: Do you agree with the Government’s proposal to introduce an option for recording Heat Transfer Coefficients based on SMETER measurements, as supplementary information about fabric performance?

Response options: strongly agree, agree, neither agree nor disagree, disagree or strongly disagree. Please provide any comments or evidence to support your answer.

Agree – Leveraging Smart Meter data as much as possible should be a priority of the HEM development team. This, however, should not be limited to the use of SMETERs.

Disagree – The Government should be thinking more in terms of integrating this as part of the mandatory assessments as opposed to the proposed “opt-in” approach. This misses the point. If the information is available to use, it should be used. Moreover, integrating this directly into the HEM methodologies, completely removes the complications around setting up “robust validation and quality assurance processes” that deal with any number of different SMETER methodologies from any number of third parties.

Section 3: Heating system metric

Question 9: Do you agree with our proposal on the design and methodology for the Heating System metric?

Response options: strongly agree, agree, neither agree nor disagree, disagree or strongly disagree. Please provide any additional comments or evidence to support your answer.

Disagree – while it is mentioned that the heating metric will use modelled estimates of heating/cooling efficiency and emissions, it is not sufficiently clear what this will entail, or whether different models will be used for different systems (they should). Moreover, the scoring and banding considerations discussed appear to describe a heuristic approach without clear indications of how any potential modelled estimates of efficiency/carbon intensity will be used for the actual scoring. This casts significant doubts on the robustness of the methodology overall.

Question 10: Do you agree with the proposal to set the C/D boundary such that direct electric will always score a D or below, and that storage-based technologies would score above or below the C/D boundary based on their emissions relative to direct electric?

Response options: strongly agree, agree, neither agree nor disagree, disagree or strongly disagree. Please provide any additional comments or evidence to support your answer.

Disagree – while there might be a case for carrying out the scoring based on such an approach, this would defeat the purpose of modelling efficiency/carbon intensity of existing heating/cooling systems. Presumably, the scoring (and corresponding banding) should be reflective of this. It is hard to reconcile, on the one hand, the intention to take all these technical details into account for modelling, and on the other, the intention to 'impose' certain bands primarily with the goal to influence responses and technology adoption. Both intentions are indeed valuable, but it would appear that more thought needs to go into the development of a methodology that allows for both objectives to be achieved in a concerted manner.

Question 11: What is your view on the option of reserving the highest scores of A/B for electric cooking appliances?

Response options: strongly agree, agree, neither agree nor disagree, disagree or strongly disagree. Do you have any views on how these should be reflected in EPCs (whether in terms of banding or advice to consumers?)

Disagree – If this metric/score is meant to be reflective of heating/cooling systems' efficiency/carbon intensity, somehow giving cooking appliances priority or a higher weighting seems at odds with the stated goal.

Section 4: Smart readiness metric

Question 12: Do you have any views on the proposed list of technologies that would be recognised under the Smart Readiness Metric and their relative scoring?

Please provide any evidence to support your answer.

Agree – the technologies listed in the consultation document seem essential to determine the 'smart readiness' of a dwelling, as defined. The list is also consistent with the set of technologies being considered as part of the Demand Flexibility Certification (DFC) framework².

Disagree – the consultation document states that it is “possible to quantitatively assess the flexibility potential and reliance on the grid as the basis for a new metric”. However, there appears to be contradicting goals for the metric. Arguably, a metric that determines the 'smart readiness' of a dwelling will not necessarily be reflective of the existing flexibility potential, because it measures the presence or capability of smart technologies rather than the actual magnitude and usability of demand-side flexibility that can be delivered to the energy system. We propose that the scope of this metric should reflect the characteristics outlined in the EDRC report on the Demand Flexibility Certification framework². The smart readiness metric should assess demand flexibility potential across two key dimensions: magnitude and quality. Focusing on these dimensions allows the metric to provide meaningful and informative insights while maintaining a manageable level of complexity. We propose

² www.edrc.ac.uk/publications/demand-flexibility-certificates

a Nominal rating that reflects the overall magnitude of the potential demand increase or decrease that could be delivered (kW). In addition, a Quality rating would indicate how readily this flexibility can be deployed, capturing factors such as response speed, frequency, and duration (e.g. response rate in kW/second, number of events per day, and duration in minutes).

The banding considerations may benefit from further clarification in relation to the intended purpose of the metric. However, the consultation document appears to suggest that a dwelling could potentially achieve a rating higher than 1 - the proposed minimum score – without foundational technologies such as a smart meter. It would therefore be helpful to better understand how the proposed banding structure aligns with the underlying objective of assessing readiness to engage with smart energy services.

Question 13: Do you have views on the options we have set out for how to achieve a C on the Smart Readiness Metric?

The banding considerations should be made on the basis of scores obtained by actual dwellings and their corresponding attributes, assets, and/or characteristics. As such, there should be a complete rethinking of the proposed 'rules' to achieve any band.

Questions 16: Do you agree that a bidirectional EV charge point should be recognised as an alternative to other forms of energy storage, such as batteries, in order to achieve a C on the Smart Readiness Metric?

Response options: strongly agree, agree, neither agree nor disagree, disagree or strongly disagree. Please provide any additional comments or evidence to support your answer.

Disagree – EV charging should not be treated as a direct alternative/replacement for dedicated electric storage.

Section 5: Energy cost metric

Question 18: Do you agree with our proposed approach to the design and methodology for the Energy Cost metric?

Response options: strongly agree, agree, neither agree nor disagree, disagree or strongly disagree. Please provide any comments or evidence to support your answer.

Neither agree nor disagree – given any total consumption estimates, a simple conversion to cost is as good a proxy. There remain questions around the usefulness of this particular ‘metric’ in the context of energy performance assessments and the potential for engaging in things like demand flexibility programmes.

Question 19: Do you agree that the cost metric should be presented in £, rather than bands?

Response options: strongly agree, agree, neither agree nor disagree, disagree or strongly disagree. Please provide any comments or evidence to support your answer.

Neither agree nor disagree – presumably, the costs should be presented in terms of ranges, where each range corresponds to a particular rating. Considering that this is the approach taken with previous metrics, the decision to change the approach here seems like an unnecessary complication.

About EDRC

The Energy Demand Research Centre (EDRC) undertakes research for an affordable and secure low energy future. Our interdisciplinary research programme identifies evidence-based energy demand reductions for a sustainable and more equitable future. We work closely with partners from policy, industry, civil society and academia.

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